

RESPONSIBLE
RESEARCH SERIES
6:2025

DECLARATION FOR OPEN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH 2025–2030

RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH SERIES

Responsible Research Series publishes declarations, policies, studies, recommendations and other documents relating to the openness, responsibility and accessibility of science and research. Publications also cover science communication and science-society interactions. The publication series is not a scientific peer-reviewed publication. The series is published by the Committee for Public Information (TJNK) and the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV).

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Responsible Research series 6:2025

7th volume

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PUBLISHER: Committee for Public Information
and The Federation of Finnish Learned Societies

Helsinki, 2025

ISSN: 2670-062X

ISBN: 978-952-7589-14-4

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.23847/tsv.1358>

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INTRODUCTION

OPENNESS IS A FUNDAMENTAL VALUE IN RESEARCH. Openness is promoted while also taking into account the other core values of research: academic freedom of research and education, reliability, research integrity and equity.

The Declaration for Open Science and Research 2025–2030 is an update to the previous Declaration for Open Science and Research 2020–2025. The declaration is elaborated in more detail by four national open science policies, which further define and explain the concepts used in the declaration.

The signatories of the declaration commit to the following objectives, while taking into account their own specific characteristics:

1. to strive for the vision of open science and research stated in the declaration in accordance with the principles of responsible openness
2. to implement the commitments outlined in the declaration in their operations, and
3. to promote the objectives of national open science policies that elaborate the declaration.

The Declaration for Open Science and Research is aligned with international guiding documents promoting openness. The declaration takes into consideration the Unesco definitions and recommendations related to open science and education, as well as a wide range of European guidelines and decisions promoting responsible openness of research. Openness also helps promote international equity and access to research-based knowledge. Through the declaration, members of the Finnish research community join in a global dialogue and network that promotes responsible open science.

The operating environment of open science is constantly changing, which is why the contents of the declaration also need to be assessed and updated regularly. This version of the declaration considers especially the rapidly changed geopolitical environment and the resulting security concerns. Even though the world is undergoing upheaval, trust in scientific collaboration and openness remains a valuable part of a safe global community built on trust.

The Declaration for Open Science and Research 2025–2030 is the result of collaborative development within the research community. Experts working under the national Open Science Coordination and key stakeholders across the research sector contributed to its drafting. The declaration was officially adopted by the National Open Science and Research Steering Group on 24 March 2025. With the updated declaration, Finland reaffirms its role as an international forerunner in open science – together and responsibly.

DECLARATION FOR OPEN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH 2025-2030

GUIDING PRINCIPLES FOR PROMOTING OPENNESS

Collaboration
and participation

Diversity and
multilingualism

Transparency
and accountability

Sustainability
and common good

VISION OF RESPONSIBLE OPENNESS

COMMITMENTS

Culture for open
scholarship

Open access to research
data and methods

Open access to
scholarly publishing

Open access
to education

GUIDING PRINCIPLES FOR PROMOTING OPENNESS

The promotion of open science and research in Finland is guided by the following principles, in particular:

Collaboration and participation, which help us determine and express the shared goals of the research community to promote openness. We invite all key stakeholders to participate and ensure that everyone has an equal opportunity to participate in co-development.

Diversity and multilingualism, which allow us to consider the specific characteristics of the organisations, and the various methods and dimensions of promoting openness. We pay special attention to multilingualism to safeguard the status of official national languages as languages of science and research.

Transparency and accountability, which help us ensure that our operations are both open and accessible. We consider the safety and freedom of speech of researchers, the needs of civil society and the importance of responsible international engagement.

Sustainability and common good, that refers to considering the UN's goals of sustainable development, our strive towards economic sustainability in promoting openness, and the acknowledgment that the benefits of science and research belong to everyone.

VISION OF RESPONSIBLE OPENNESS

- Openness enables equitable access to research outputs and participation in science.
- Openness promotes intellectual and cultural development and the societal use of research.
- Openness contributes to ensure the transparency and reproducibility of research, therefore increasing its reliability.
- Openness supports the impact, quality and diversity of research, education and administration, as well as innovation and development, in a sustainable way while also promoting the versatile utilisation and reuse of the research outputs.
- Openness is such an integral part of teaching, research and development that it is no longer necessary to highlight open science as a separate concept.
- Promotion of openness is a community-led effort. Finland is part of the international group of forerunners of openness.

COMMITMENTS

By signing the declaration, the signatories from the higher education and research community commit to the following objectives, while taking into account their own specific characteristics:

1. Culture for open scholarship

- 1.1. We develop and maintain the practices and services of responsible openness in research, teaching and development and innovation.
- 1.2. We recognise societal interaction of research, company collaboration, citizen science and other participatory practices as merits in the assessment and career advancement.

2. Open access to scholarly publishing

- 2.1. We promote immediate open access of scholarly publications and their long-term availability in an economically sustainable way.
- 2.2. We enable the use of various open access publication channels and formats, as well as multilingual scholarly publishing.
- 2.3. We acknowledge the work done for promoting the quality, openness and diversity of scholarly publications in the assessment and career advancement.

3. Open access to research data and methods

- 3.1. We implement the principle that research data, methods and infrastructures should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary.
- 3.2. We manage the research data and methods and the research infrastructures in a way that allows the implementation of FAIR principles.
- 3.3. We recognise research data and methods as independent research outputs that are considered in the assessment and career advancement.

4. Open access to education

- 4.1. We integrate open educational practices and open educational resources into higher education.
- 4.2. We acknowledge work that promotes open education in assessment and career advancement.

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Learned Societies**